

Micro-Certification Research On Educational Practice Ability Of Normal University Students

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Abstract

This study focuses on micro-certification of teacher training students' educational practice ability, sorting out relevant research results, firstly, using the Delphi method and validating factor analysis to construct a micro-competency index system for teacher training students' educational practice, and after conducting Delphi three times, the overall mean reached the very important to important level, and the indexes covered four first-level dimensions, nine second-level dimensions of teacher moral practice ability, teaching ability, nurturing ability, and development ability, totaling The validation factor analysis showed that the micro-competency index system had high reliability and validity and reasonable distribution of entries. Then, based on the 31 micro-competency dimensions, we constructed a standardized framework for teacher education practice micro-competency certification according to the micro-certification development framework of "Competency Center - Evidence Driven - Task Grasp", and designed a micro-certification operation model for teacher education practice competency. The practical results show that it can better meet the needs of teacher-training students' educational practice ability assessment and educational teaching ability improvement, and can support teacher-training students' professional learning and the cultivation of independent learning ability. Finally, the study concludes that: 1. the identified competency index system can comprehensively reflect the educational practice competency of practicing teacher educators; 2. the specification and operation model of teacher education practice competency certification based on micro-certification are scientific and feasible; 3. the micro-certification model of teacher education practice competency is simple and universal, and clearly defines the connotation and extension of teacher education practice competency. It allows teachers from different disciplinary and professional backgrounds to interpret the four dimensions to be developed, which can realize the sustainable development of teacher education practice competency.

Introduction

This paper aims to explore the theoretical and research findings related to this study as a basis for discussing the research results. This section is divided into six sections. This section is divided into six sections: Section 1 is the theoretical foundation of this study, Section 2 is the research on micro-certification, Section 3 is the research on teacher education standards, and Section 4 is the research on educational practice competencies.

Theoretical foundations of this study

The development and implementation of micro-certification benefited from the foundation of related theories, mainly including informal learning theory, learning motivation theory, competency-based learning theory, and an evidence-centered assessment design model.

Informal Learning Theories

The existence of many ambiguities in the definitions of Informal Learning and Formal Learning has led to contradictions and disagreements among scholars (Czerkawski, 2016). Informal Cross (2007) defines informal learning as "an informal, unplanned, and improvised way of learning like riding a bicycle, where the learner chooses the destination, speed, and route." The learner decides what they need to learn and then establishes their own learning goals and agenda, decides when they should learn, chooses the format and approach that best suits their needs, and takes responsibility for organizing and managing his or her own learning-related activities. Boileau (2011) states that informal learning is when people spontaneously engage in relevant activities in a work environment, by completing work or tasks acquiring new skills and knowledge. In other words, informal learning is meaningful experience that builds on existing experiences and pre-existing knowledge structures, thereby facilitating the development of new tacit and exogenous knowledge. To fully engage learners

and ensure knowledge transfer, informal learning should be authentic, ideally occurring in the workplace or other performance setting, in a meaningful environment that builds on prior knowledge, and employs strategies and activities that facilitate knowledge transfer (Boileau, 2011). Merriam and Bierema (2014) identify four types of learning in informal learning, including self-directed, incidental, tacit, and integrative learning. In contrast to formal learning, the learning objectives and curriculum are determined by others. In informal learning learners decide the knowledge and skills to be learned based on authentic problems. Among Chinese scholars, Wu Lijuan and Huang Jingwen define informal learning from the perspective of learning motivation, which is a form of learning triggered by internal psychological or external contextual touch, it has a clear intention to learn, it is to solve the current problems encountered, its content structure of learning is loose, the capacity of each learning knowledge module is small, and learning occurs in the formation of learning needs, generating learning motivation and having learning opportunities. Learning occurs anywhere that learning needs are formed, motivation is generated, and learning opportunities are available. Zhu Zhiting and Zhang Hao define informal learning in terms of the form of teaching and learning, which is usually unofficial. It may be purposeful or inadvertent behavior, it does not have a formal teacher in the usual sense, it is mostly not evaluated by grades or graded, and the measure of learning effectiveness is success or failure in life or work. Defined from the perspective of learning mode, it is believed that informal learning is relative to formal schooling or continuing education, and refers to the form of learning in informal learning time and place such as work, life, and social life to receive new knowledge, mainly referring to learning by doing, learning by playing, and learning by touring, such as salon, reading, partying, playing ball, etc. Defined from the perspective of learning content, informal learning is considered to be individual self-learning in the full sense of the word, referring to the learning activities that learners personally carry out consciously to achieve their desired goals or meet their needs in work, life and interests, from the determination of learning goals and the selection of learning content to the mastery of learning progress and the adoption of learning methods and approaches, all of which are determined by the individual learners. A growing number of researchers are concerned with studying the breadth and depth of informal learning applied to adult learning, with 70-90% of learning occurring through informal learning activities throughout the lifespan (Merriam and Bierema, 2014). Falk and Dierking (2010) suggest that 95% of science learning behaviors occur outside of school.

Microtraining, microlearning, and digital badges are often considered to be important ways of informal learning. Microtraining combines formal learning activities with informal learning activities close to the real world, utilizes short learning sessions that can usually be completed in a 15-minute time frame, and is designed to rapidly develop and disseminate knowledge (De Vries and Brall, 2008). According to De Vries and Brall (2008), microtraining combines semi-formal learning activities with informal and ad hoc learning processes that include activation of prior knowledge, demonstration and practice, feedback sessions, and transfer strategies.

Microlearning is an urgent informal learning strategy designed to quickly bridge gaps in knowledge and skills when completing a task. The most common medium for microlearning is Web 2.0 technologies on mobile devices, consisting of short bursts of interconnected and loosely coupled learning activities with a narrow thematic focus (Buchem and Hamelmann, 2010). In other words, microlearning tends to build depth of knowledge rather than breadth of knowledge, can be applied to a wide range of learning types, goals, preferences, and theoretical frameworks (e.g., cognitivism, constructivism, connectionism), and is a hybrid of informal and formal learning activities.

With digital badges, informal learning opportunities are increasing with the needs of different industries and disciplines and personal and professional development, and many learners are faced with the question of how to recognize the achievements of informal learning (Law, 2015). Digital badges acknowledge participation and achievement in informal learning activities and are used to demonstrate learning effectiveness, such as completion of a mini-training learning component. The use of digital badges can also be seen in formal learning in educational institutions as a motivational tool and in the form of micro-credentials in an incremental trend in various educational settings. The amount of OER content used to support informal learning has grown exponentially in recent years to support micro-learning. With the increase in OER, different business models have emerged to support the distribution of digital open badges. For example, learners can access OER content for free through various MOOC (Massive Open Online Course) service providers, such as EdX and Coursera. These services offer hundreds of free courses.

Learning Motivation Theory

Learning Motivation (LM) is an internal motivation driven by internal (intrinsic) or external (extrinsic) forces that stimulate and sustain individual learning activities and move the activities toward a specific learning goal, and is a type of achievement motivation. Teachers are the best source of motivation in teaching interactions. Graham and Weiner (1996) state that learners who are strongly motivated are more committed to learning. Motivation can be divided into intrinsic motivation, extrinsic motivation and motivation, learning is a complex process and learning motivation is one of the important factors that influence learning activities, T. Li, and R. Lynch (2016) stated that intrinsic motivation leads to self-motivation to pursue learning, while extrinsic motivation gives the purpose to pursue learning. The self-efficacy, achievement goal, and expectancy theories of

learning motivation theory are supported by a large body of empirical research.

Achievement goal theory argues that all motivation is related to a person's goal orientation. Dweck (1978) starts from the purpose of behavior and divides people's goals into mastery goal orientation and achievement goal orientation, and corresponds to different evaluation criteria. Achievement goals are based on self-satisfaction by looking smart or gaining superiority in front of peers. Mastery goals are motivated by the desire to fully master a skill or concept, and students with mastery goals will complete the project when they are proud of it, not when it meets minimum requirements. They are likely to continue to reflect and make improvements even after they have turned in the task to be assessed. Individuals with mastery goals have stronger internal motivation than those with achievement goals. Mastery goals are largely aligned with intrinsic motivation, and purpose orientation exerts a strong influence on persistence through a rigorous task.

Expectancy theory was developed by W. Van Eerde and H. Thierry. The theory was developed based on the work environment to motivate employees and was later extended and revised by P.H. HemaMalini and A. Washington. Expectancy theory focuses more on motivation and its connection to each individual (P.H. HemaMalini and A. Washington, 2014). Exciting force refers to the intensity of motivating an individual and stimulating the person's internal potential; expectancy is the degree of certainty of reaching a goal as judged by the individual's experience; and efficacy is the value of the goal that can be reached to satisfy the individual's needs. The more certain a person is about a goal, the higher the estimated probability of reaching the goal, the stronger the motivation is and the greater the motivation is. Effort, performance, and intrinsic attractiveness are interrelated with human motivation (W. Van Eerde and H. Thierry, 1996). This theory is more about external rewards and appreciation. There are several stages before receiving a reward; first, the student must be fully motivated and believe that he can only give sincere and maximum effort to obtain acceptable performance, then performance will be rewarded, and finally, the value of the reward is completely positive. The final stage of expectancy theory is known as intrinsic attraction (K.N. Bauer, K.A. Orvis, K. Ely, and E.A. Surface, 2016). Li Yanping and Guo Dejun (2000) suggested that realistic, specific, short-term learning goals can increase students' confidence in completing tasks and willingness to put effort into completing them. Yang Pan (2020) pointed out that micro-certification is based on the theory of learning motivation, and learners with internal motivation tend to enjoy the process of professional learning and the sense of accomplishment brought by the learning process in micro-certification; learners with external motivation can avoid punishment or obtain rewards through micro-certification, such as earning on-the-job "credits" (credits) and salary increase, etc. credits) and salary increases, etc.

Competency-Based Learning

Competency based learning (CBL) has been widely used in the United States. The definition of competency-based learning is complex, and some of the more common synonyms include proficiency education, mastery education, outcomes education, performance education, and standards education, instruction, and learning. Competency-based learning refers to systems of instruction, assessment, grading, and academic reporting that are based on students demonstrating that they have learned the knowledge and skills they are expected to learn during the educational process. In a competency-based educational framework, students demonstrate the knowledge and skills they have learned to achieve specific predetermined "competencies". A set of competencies for a particular curriculum or a particular educational institution is sometimes referred to as a competency framework. The key concepts that make up a competency-based educational framework include mastery of competencies, meaningful types of assessment, individualized support for students, and the creation and application of knowledge. In CBL, learners first identify their competencies and develop their own learning plan with the guidance of a mentor; learners then work alone online, being assessed on a variety of competencies at different stages of the course, often with the opportunity to try specific competencies multiple times, and receiving ongoing feedback from the mentor. If the test or assessment demonstrates that the learner has mastered a particular competency or skill, then the learner can move on to the next stage of learning without having to follow an established schedule. Thus, the learning process often allows different students to move at different speeds through the course. (Gervais, J, 2016)

The general goal of competency-based learning is to ensure that students acquire the knowledge and skills necessary to succeed in school, higher education, career, and adult life. If students fail to meet expected learning standards, they are typically provided with additional instruction, practice time, and academic support to help them gain competencies or meet expected standards. The goal of competency-based learning is to ensure that more students learn what they are expected to learn, but this approach can also provide educators with more detailed information about student learning progress, helping them to more accurately identify academic strengths and weaknesses, as well as specific concepts and skills that students have not yet mastered. Because academic progress is often tracked and reported by learning standards in competency-based programs and schools, educators and parents often know more accurately what specific knowledge and skills students have acquired or may be working toward mastering. For example, rather than receiving a score on an assignment or test that may involve a variety of criteria, students are scored according to specific In a competency-based learning model, teachers need to identify specific learning outcomes in terms of behavior and performance,

including the appropriate level of criteria to use in assessing achievement.

Weifei and Zhiting Zhu (2017) suggest that the planning of micro-certification coincides with the philosophy of CBL, where the same focus on mastery of competencies is also present. Micro-certification is not only about meeting accountability requirements for "time in class" for teacher professional development, but also about mapping teachers' professional development to a competency-based system that observes teachers' professional development and collects their achievements in professional development. Micro-certification differs from the "process participation" mindset of Chinese teachers' professional development in that it highlights the concept of "competency-based" education, cares more about the results achieved in education and teaching practice, and gives teachers the autonomy to choose their own learning goals, learning resources, and learning methods. It also gives teachers the right to make their own choices in terms of learning goals, learning resources, and learning methods, in order to solve the current problems in teachers' professional development and to build and innovate a professional development environment for teachers.

Evidence-centered evaluation design model

"EvidenceCentered Design (ECD) is a model of systematic evaluation design proposed by Robert J. Mislevy and others, and has become one of the major research directions and application models in the field of educational evaluation in the United States. ECD is a framework for designing and developing assessments that aims to provide structure and rigor to the assessment development process and to generate evidence of assessment validity by tightly coupling assessment tasks with focused knowledge, skills, and abilities, ensuring that validity evidence is considered and collected from the beginning of test design. The ECD framework defines several interrelated models, namely the student model, the evidence model, and the task model (the three models ECD translates an argument into the design of an assessment mechanism based on three models: the student model, the evidence model, and the task model, i.e., tasks, rules, statistical models, etc. The ECD framework is also referred to as the conceptual assessment framework, CAF.

Concept of micro-certification

An innovative, educator-oriented micro-credentialing system (Micro-credentials), announced in 2014 by the U.S. nonprofit organization Digital Promise, certifies teachers on specific, well-defined competencies based on assessing educators' performance in practice to identify skills that educators have acquired over their careers that enhance student learning experiences, recognizes educators' career achievement, and regardless of when, where, and through what mode of learning (formal or informal) the skill was acquired (Digital Promise, 2016a). Although micro-certification has been present in vocational education for many years, with the explosion of Covid-19, online teaching and learning has now moved from vocational education to the center of higher education policy as the latest tool to reposition higher education as focused on work readiness ((OECD-Kato et al., 2020, p. 8; see also, UNESCO-Chakroun & Keevy, 2018; European Commission-MicroHE Consortium, n.d.; Commonwealth of Learning -Rossiter & Tynan, 2019). For example, the New Zealand Qualifications Framework now includes micro-credentials (New Zealand Qualifications Authority, 2018), and the Australian government has introduced a new type of qualification in response to the 2020 Covid-19 pandemic, called the 'under-graduate higher education certificate' that is valid for six months (Commonwealth of Australia, 2020). The Canadian province of Ontario has proposed that micro-credentialing will increase flexibility and responsiveness to student and employer needs (Government of Ontario, 2020). International governmental organizations such as UNESCO (Chakroun & Keevy, 2018) and OECD (Kato et al., 2020) are focusing on micro-certification as is the European Commission, and the European MOOC Consortium has launched a generic micro-certification framework to "create portable certificates for lifelong learners" (Konings, 2019).

Micro-credentials are generally considered to be mini-qualifications, short-term industry-aligned learning units that are largely work or socially driven, providing a clear, achievable goal where learners demonstrate specific knowledge, skills or competencies through a short, validated course or learning experience , providing learners with a digital certification such as a "digital badge ". After certification or accreditation, they can be (mostly) "stacked" or counted towards higher education qualifications,. Micro-credentialing is an expression of competency-based education (CBE) designed to link certification with specific skills practice, done in offline, online or blended learning, and is considered a new type of educational ecosystem for lifelong learning and overcoming existing skills gaps.

Conclusion

Digital Promise's "micro-credentialing" is recognized by many teacher professional development organizations. Micro-certification for teachers is a competency-based certification system for educators that promotes teacher competency development as the central task of teacher education and is a model of classroom professional development that organizes instruction according to professional competency needs. It is a way for teachers to demonstrate professional growth. Micro-certification is generally considered to have the following characteristics (Digital Promise, 2016b): (1) Modularity and stackability: Micro-certification is usually composed of several learning modules (lessons, units, courses). Learners are able to combine and re-bundle

them according to their individual needs/interests, with the potential for greater achievement if they wish. (2) Personalized: Micro-certifications enable the selection of appropriate professional development courses based on specific student needs and school-wide pedagogical goals, in accordance with individual learning paths, learning time and development needs, and demonstrate the acquisition of professional competencies in a diverse manner. (3) Competency-based: The competencies in the micro-credentialing system are independent, specific, and explicit, enabling learners to focus on discrete skills relevant to their practice and to gather evidence, such as classroom videos or student work, to demonstrate competency in that particular skill. (4) On-demand: Through a flexible online platform that clearly identifies the competencies and required evidence for each micro-credential, learners can begin and continue to earn micro-credentials in their own time.

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